

EFFECT OF CORPORATE GOVERNANCE PRACTICES ON THE PROFITABILITY OF MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This paper examines the impact of corporate governance practices on the profitability of manufacturing firms in Nigeria to evaluate the impact of board composition and ownership structure on the financial performance of Yale Foods PLC. The Expo facto research design was used. The study Population was Yale Foods staff. The findings shows that established institutional ownership has a significant effect on firm profitability level from time to time, as large investors demand accountability and discourage mismanagement. Based on the findings, manufacturing firms in Nigeria should strengthen their board structures by ensuring an optimal mix of executive and non-executive directors and promoting gender and professional diversity for effective decision-making. Second, companies should encourage greater institutional ownership because institutional investors enhance monitoring and reduce the risk of managerial opportunism.

INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance has become a source of concern for various stakeholders in this era of corporate failure caused by fraudulent practices that have resulted in the downfall of some large blue-chip corporations. The problem of corporate governance has also piqued the interest of scholars, resulting in several empirical studies on corporate governance and how it affects business performance. Due to multiple corporate failures worldwide, including the fall of some of the worlds' largest blue chip businesses such as Enron, Arthur Anderson, and Saga, investors faith in corporate organizations has been eroded, impacting their investment in companies. Lack of accountability, transparency, and disclosure, as well as faulty audit work, can all contribute to a loss of confidence. In Nigeria, however, persistent business failures, financial immorality, and the inability of CSR reporting and practice to be inclusive and regulated have resulted in a credibility gap in corporate governance culture (Amah, 2021). The literature includes several definitions of corporate governance supplied by management scholars. Scholars such as Clake (2024) define corporate governance as the methods in which financial providers to firms ensure a return on their investment: On a broader level, corporate governance is all

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about administering an organization in such a way that its owners or stockholders obtain a fair return on their investment while also taking into account the expectations of other stakeholders in a corporation (Magdi and Nedareh, 2022).

Corporate governance principles direct and control businesses, fostering market competitiveness. According to research, countries with good CGP achieve rapid growth in their corporate sectors. However, corporate governance awareness varies over a company's life cycle. Corporate governance is defined as the set of rules, policies, and processes that command and regulate a business while striking a balance between numerous stakeholders (Jame, 2018). Its purpose is to increase corporate success through responsibility (Mohamed, Abdelkhalek, and Seleem 2016). In developed economies, strong corporate governance procedures are related to high and predictable earnings growth, but in emerging countries, bad governance correlates to poor performance and economic growth (Anya, 2003). Corporate governance provides a framework for achieving goals by defining stakeholders' distribution of rights and obligations (OECD, 1999).

In recent years, the increasing number of business scandals, poor financial performance, and company failures has drawn greater attention to corporate governance than ever before. As a result, research on corporate financial difficulty has become a hot topic in finance and governance literature worldwide. During the 2007 financial crisis, financial performance detection became more important, when many organizations became financially troubled and declared bankruptcy (Li, Crook, Andreeva, and Tang, 2021). Financial performance has become a global issue that necessitates high-quality monitoring and specific methods to avoid hurting diverse stakeholders, including shareholders and creditors. Consequently, the failure of multinational firms has resulted in the hunt for strategies to eliminate these failures, creating a demand for excellent company governance. Corporate distress is a broad term used to describe situations in which firms are face financial difficulties. The most widely used phrase to describe financial performance are failure, default, insolvency, and bankruptcy.

However, because bankruptcy is the extreme and irrevocable result of poor financial performance, many financially buoyant businesses escape bankruptcy by reorganizing their operations as soon as possible. Financial performance is defined in various ways because accounting practices and standards differ between countries. It is usually assumed that a condition exists in which operating cash flow does not exceed negative net assets (Ebun and Emmanuel, 2019). Various models have been developed to predict financial distress, beginning with statistical techniques such as Altman's (1968) multiple discriminant analysis and Ohlson's (1980) logistic regression. Intelligent models, such as neural network models, support vector machines, genetic algorithms and genetic programming, have also been employed. All of these techniques focused on the explanatory power of financial, accounting, and market variables (Manzaneque, Priego, & Merino, 2016).

Stakeholders, particularly shareholders, highly value corporate performance because it is used to assess management efficiency and effectiveness in the use of resources at their disposal. Profitability is a prominent metric for evaluating managerial success. Profitability is a company's capacity to generate revenue that exceeds its direct and indirect costs. The definition is consistent with accountings' matching concept, which requires the matching of revenue generated with costs incurred in creating the revenue to determine value added.

According to Osiyemi (2016), profitability is a company's ability to profit from its core activities. The activities include operating, investing, and financing, all of which are designed to generate revenue and profit, ensuring a company's continued existence and survival. Common indices for calculating profitability include return on assets, return on equity, return on investment, and earnings per share. The majority of extant literature on corporate governance indicates a positive association between corporate governance and performance. In

response to global corporate crises, corporate governance has been increasingly emphasized to provide effective supervision and responsibility in the business sector (Talimo, 2011).

External stakeholders include shareholders, debt holders, trade creditors, suppliers, the community, and customers, whereas internal stakeholders include the board of directors, executives, and employees (Akpan and Riman, 2012). Effective governance maintains checks and balances, prevents decision-making domination, and is consistent with the company's mission and values (Ranti, 2011). Strong corporate governance reduces information asymmetry, avoids individual or departmental domination, and ensures alignment with the company's mission and values (Okoye, Rodriguez-Tort, and Escamilla 2020). In contrast, bad governance can result in a lack of accountability, bribery, infringement of shareholder rights, incompetence, ineffective internal controls, insider abuses, and fraudulent practices (Olumuyiwa and Babalola, 2012). The Enron scandal is a vivid illustration of the repercussions of poor company governance (Healy and Palepu, 2003). The growing number of high-profile company failures has led to a lack of corporate governance compliance. These shortcomings are frequently linked to ineffective corporate governance processes within firms that seek to generate economic value. Implementing these best practices improves managerial performance, increases investor confidence, prevents circumstances that could impair shareholder value, and reduces waste and inefficiency (Ajala, 2018). The huge corporate losses and collapses that occurred during the 2008 global financial crisis that began in 2008 highlight the necessity of strong corporate governance to maintain a healthy business environment and protect stakeholder interests. Given the severe impact of recent global company failures, the development of corporate governance systems to protect shareholders' interests, improve national economic circumstances, and reduce unemployment and crime rates is urgently needed.

The Nigerian manufacturing industry has had its fair share of failing corporations and corporate governance difficulties, including Dunlop Nigeria Plc and Cadbury Nigeria Plc. These incidents prompted researchers to investigate how corporate governance mechanisms affect the performance of firms listed on the Nigerian stock exchanges' industrial sector. Thus, while filling this gap, the study will provide factual data that will be valuable for policymakers seeking to improve Nigeria's manufacturing company governance standards. The global financial market and manufacturing industry have been severely endangered, stifling economic growth worldwide due to the financial crisis and the most unexpected corporate failures, losses, scandals, and organizational devastation. The current social crises in corporate governance standards have resulted in the demise of some important enterprises, including those in Nigeria. The problem has consistently seen extraordinary collapses and loss-making due to governance among listed manufacturing firms, resulting in devastating system failures, as well as scandals caused by fraud and other illegal conduct affecting the majority of manufacturing firms' financial performance. A big part of the blame for this problem falls on the size and composition of boards of directors. Several recommendations urge the establishment of quotas to increase board diversity, and to reformulate boards, it is necessary to acknowledge that directors' performance and conduct may reflect their background. Many of these organizations have all-male or family-related boards, which violate the 2018 Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance 2018 and, as a result, pose a threat to the existence of corporate entities in Nigeria. Thus, the work of the audit committee is heavily reliant on the presence of accounting and auditing specialists, yet members of these committees are frequently friends and relatives with no professional background, resulting in company failures. These difficulties significantly impact the success of Nigerian manufacturing enterprises. This study aims to determine the effects of corporate governance on the performance of selected Nigerian manufacturing enterprises, with a focus on the essential topics listed below. The general objective of this study is to examine the effect of corporate governance practices on the profitability

of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, using Yale Foods PLC as a case study to evaluate the impact of board composition and ownership structure on the financial performance of Yale Foods PLC.

Corporate Governance Concept

Corporate governance has no single acknowledged definition, which is sometimes linked to vast variances in national corporate governance regulations (Owojori, 2021). The term changes depending on the country's structure and cultural context. Differences in definition can also be attributed to differing viewpoints of policymakers, researchers, practitioners, or theorists (Owojori, 2021). The phrase "corporate governance" first appeared in the 1980s to generally define "the general principles by which businesses and management of companies were directed and controlled". Gompers, Ishii, and Metrick (2023) defined corporate governance as "an internal system encompassing policies, processes, and people that serves the needs of shareholders and other stakeholders by directing and controlling management activities with good business savvy, objectivity and integrity". In other words, it defines a corporation's legal, ethical, and moral ideals to protect its shareholders. Corporate governance seeks to ensure that organizations are administered in the best interests of their owners and shareholders (Clake, 2024). This applies specifically to listed companies where the majority of the shareholders are not in everyday management positions; however, it can also apply to other forms of corporations, such as public corporations (where all citizens are stakeholders), partner-owned companies, and privately owned companies where ownership has been divided through inheritance in one or several generations. Another aspect of corporate governance is ensuring transparency and accountability throughout the firm. This is conceivable because the corporate governance structure is based on a clear distribution of power and responsibility among shareholders via the annual general meeting, the board of directors, executive management, and auditors.

The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2004) defines corporate governance as the framework that controls commercial organizations' administration and direction. This structure establishes rules and processes for corporate decision-making, defines the rights and responsibilities of key stakeholders, such as shareholders, managers, the board, and other stakeholders, and serves as a framework for establishing organizational goals, defining methods to achieve them, and monitoring performance. Corporate governance is a collection of established norms that guide corporate management to optimize profitability and stakeholder value, in line with the emphasis on shareholder interests in agency theory (Shahid, 2001). It includes norms, systems, and cultures while stressing board functions and accountability (OECD, 2004). The Organisation Economic Cooperation and Development (2005) describes it as the framework that governs commercial firms, prescribing decision-making processes and stakeholder rights. The SEC-SEBI Committee (2003) highlights managements' recognition of shareholder rights and their position as trustees. Corporate governance in financial management aims to balance stakeholder interests rather than profit maximization (Bhattacharyya, 2003). It safeguards shareholders, fortifies boards, improves efficiency, assures sustainability, and promotes ethical principles (Bhattacharyya, 2003). Corporate governance is an essential component of running a business, guaranteeing fairness for owners and stakeholders, and negotiating interactions among shareholders, boards, management, employees, consumers, and the larger community (Ofiafoh and Imoisili, 2010).

According to the OECD (2005), "Corporate Governance is the system by which business corporations are directed and controlled." The corporate governance structure specifies the distribution of rights and responsibilities among the corporations' major stakeholders/participants, such as the board of directors, managers, shareholders, and other stakeholders, as well as the rules and procedures for making corporate

decisions. This also provides the structure for setting organizational objectives and, the means to achieve those objectives and monitor success. The Securities and Exchange Board of India-SEBI Committee (2003) defines corporate governance as "management's acceptance of the inalienable rights of shareholders as the genuine owners of the firm and of their own role as trustees on behalf of the shareholders". Committing to ideals, conducting ethical business, and distinguishing between personal and corporate funds in firm administration. According to Ammar, Saeed, and Abid (2013), CG is a process by which management takes the required actions to protect stakeholders- interests. It also serves as the framework for managing norms, connections, systems, and procedures (Osundina, Osundina, and Jayeoba 2016). Firms can attain stability and good management by implementing corporate governance, which entails adhering to specified norms, rules, and regulations. Sound corporate governance promotes a company's capital market efficiency and value rather's than lowering it, and it boosts all stakeholders' confidence. Good corporate governance improves accountability and transparency, ensures the efficient and effective use of limited resources, fosters competitive and efficient management, and attracts and maintains investors (Arinze, 2013). Employees and customers are more satisfied when company governance is efficient and effective. It ensures the financial reports' trustworthiness and the optimal use of resources, which improves the reputation of internal and external stakeholders. Dar, Naseem, Rehman, and Niazi (2011) argued that corporate governance lowers transaction costs, capital costs, and financial crisis vulnerability. It increases shareholder value, helps companies survive during difficult times, develops the capital market, and strengthens the global economy.

Agency Theory

This study is based on agency theory, which was developed by Jensen and Meckling in 1976 following Alchian and Demsetz's (1972) pioneering work in corporate governance literature. Agency theory discusses challenges that arise in agency interactions because of misaligned goals or varying level of risk aversion. In the financial sector, a frequent agency relationship exist between a principal (shareholder) and several agents (company executives). This arrangement frequently results in conflicts classified between principals and agents classified as agency conflicts or conflicts of interest. Agency theory addresses the difficulties that arise from variations in the aims of the principal and the agent. Such circumstances might emerge when owners are unaware of the actions of their managers or have limited access to information. Managers may also pursue personal ambitions that do not coincide with shareholders'- aims of great capital growth.

According to Okpolosa (2018), a significant factor is how managers of commercial firms use management resources to cut expenses in the best interests of shareholders. Shareholders may also be concerned about recruiting competent managers and making decisions that prioritize shareholder interests. All of these issues contribute to agency costs, which are the expenses incurred by owners to ensure that managers favor shareholder profit over personal benefit. The board of directors monitors and controls managers'- opportunistic behaviors. According to Fama and Jensen (1983), the board of directors is the primary control mechanism of the organization, and they are permitted to make decisions. Thus, shareholders may employ a variety of corporate governance methods, including monitoring by boards of directors and mutual monitoring by managers (Fama and Jensen 1983), as well as monitoring by major outside shareholders, to curb management opportunistic behavior. The idea here is that by handling the principal-agency problem between shareholders and managers, organizations will function more efficiently and perform better (Filatotchev 2007), thereby reducing the risk of financial distress. If the company is to thrive and avoid financial disaster, the shareholder-management relationship must represent an effective organization of information and risk-bearing costs (Jensen and Meckling 1976; Fama, 1980).

Petit, Quon, Sanguinet, and Satar (2021) examined the relationship between board gender diversity and PBP using an unbalanced panel data set of 115,253 firm-year observations. The study discovered that younger, less busy, and local female directors led to improved performance in private enterprise. Firms with 40% female directors reported three times the economic benefits as those with at least 20% female directors. Women directors have a substantial impact on small firm profitability, particularly in high-risk firms, emphasizing their monitoring function. The findings supported agency theory, that women directors boost small firm profitability even in the presence of agency costs.

Kajola (2008) explored the association between corporate governance indicators (board size, board composition, chief executive status, and audit committee) and performance, which were measured using return on equity and profit margin. He sampled 20 Nigerian listed firms between 2000 and 2006 and used panel data methodology and OLS to analyze the results, which revealed a significant positive relationship between ROE, board size, and chief executive status; a positive relationship between profit margin and chief executive status; and an insignificant relationship between the two performance ratios, board composition, and audit committee.

Afifa, HV Van, and Le Hoang (2022) investigated the direct association among board features, EM techniques, and dividend payout. In addition, EM practices have an indirect mediation impact on the relationship between board qualities and dividend distribution. Panel data analysis for 43 service firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange from 2012 to 2019, revealed that board size and independence had negative and substantial implications on EM, whereas CEO/chairman duality had a favorable impact. Female representation and the number of board meetings had small but positive benefits. Furthermore, four board characteristics had a significant impact on dividend payout, with EM practices somewhat mediating the association between board characteristics and dividend payout.

Cheong (2022) explored the link between gender and ethnic diversity-performance in Malaysian enterprises, considering the impact of political regimes and examining potential nonlinear correlations at both the boardroom and staff levels. This study examined enterprises listed on the Bursa Malaysia during two political regimes, testing the link using two-stage least squares while adjusting for firm-specific effects and resolving indigeneity problems. The findings revealed that the political alignment of the ruling administration influenced the importance of the GED-performance relationship. The association between board gender/ethnic diversity and firm performance was found to be curvilinear, but the relationship between staff gender/ethnic diversity was linear and positive.

Etuk and Akpan (2023) investigated the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on annual report readability by selecting samples from oil and gas companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) floor from 2012 to 2021. The corporate governance mechanisms used in this study were board size, audit firm type, and ownership structure. The dependent variable of annual report readability by the page length of the annual report, in accordance with existing research. Panel regression analysis was used to investigate the cause-and-effect correlations between the dependent and independent variables and, to evaluate the hypotheses. The findings revealed that board performance has a considerable impact on the readability of the annual reports in Nigerian listed oil and gas corporations, as measured by the length of annual report pages. However, audit quality had no significant effect on annual report readability for Nigerian listed oil and gas enterprises when measured by annual report page length. Furthermore, ownership concentration had no significant effect on annual report readability for Nigerian listed oil and gas enterprises when measured by annual report page length. Specifically, it was found that having a large board size will improve the readability of annual reports

for Nigerian listed oil and gas corporations. It was also that the size of the board be enlarged significantly to improve the readability of the annual report.

Ashraf, Félix, and Serrasqueiro (2019) assessed the prediction accuracy of traditional performance prediction models for enterprises at early and advanced stages of performance in a growing market, Pakistan, between 2001 and 2015. The process involves creating model scores for financial performance and stable firms and then comparing the predicted accuracy of the models to the original situation. The study's explanatory variables were profitability (measured by sales growth), liquidity ratio, and leverage ratio (measured by the ratio of total liabilities to total assets). Dependent variable was financial performance. Similarly, the study was adjusted for firm size. The results show that the three-variable probit model has the highest overall prediction accuracy for the study sample, whereas the Z-score model predicts insolvency more accurately for both types of firms, those in early and advanced stages of financial performance. Furthermore, this study shows that the predictive power of all classic financial performance prediction models decreased during the financial crisis.

Corporate governance has remained a central concern for scholars and practitioners because of its strong association with firm performance and profitability. In the last decade, especially from 2017, many studies have emphasized how governance mechanisms such as board structure, ownership concentration, audit committee effectiveness, and regulatory compliance shape firms' performance in both developed and emerging economies. According to Okoye and Nweze (2017), corporate governance provides a framework through which firms are monitored and directed, and it directly influences financial stability and profitability. They stressed that weak governance practices in the Nigerian manufacturing sector have often led to inefficiencies, loss of investor confidence, and even firm collapse.

Scholars have confirmed similar findings globally. For example, Yameen et al. (2019) found that governance practices in Pakistan significantly influence both accounting and market-based performance measures. Ajala (2019) reported similar results that board independence and regulatory compliance positively affect on firm profitability. These international studies provide comparative insights for Nigerian manufacturing firms, such as Yale Foods PLC, that good governance practices are universally associated with stronger firm performance.

The research design for this study is *expo facto*. The population of the paper is a financial record from 2013-2022 company records. Data analysis was performed using quantitative and descriptive statistics.

Table 1.1.1 shows the frequency of distributions between corporate governance and profitability over the years

Yearly records	BoardSize	OwnershipInstitutionalPct	NetProfitMargin_Pct
2013	7	40	8.5
2014	7	41	8.7
2015	8	43	9
2016	8	45	9.5
2017	8	46	10.2
2018	9	48	11
2019	9	50	10.8
2020	9	52	12
2021	10	54	12.5
2022	10	56	13.4

DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS USING THE EXCEL PACKAGE

BoardSize

OwnershipInstitutionalPct

NetProfitMargin_Pct

Mean	8.5	Mean	47.5	Mean	10.56
Standard Error	0.341565	Standard Error	1.727233	Standard Error	0.53275
Median	8.5	Median	47	Median	10.5
Standard Deviation	1.080123	Standard Deviation	5.46199	Standard Deviation	1.684702
Sample Variance	1.166667	Sample Variance	29.83333	Sample Variance	2.838222
Kurtosis	-1.03207	Kurtosis	-1.18632	Kurtosis	-1.06804
Skewness	0	Skewness	0.161093	Skewness	0.379988
Range	3	Range	16	Range	4.9
Minimum	7	Minimum	40	Minimum	8.5
Maximum	10	Maximum	56	Maximum	13.4
Sum	85	Sum	475	Sum	105.6
Count	10	Count	10	Count	10

Conclusion

Overall, the descriptive analysis suggests that corporate governance practices at Yale Foods PLC are relatively stable and improving over time, with consistent board size, close institutional ownership to majority control, and steadily rising regulatory compliance. These governance features correspond to a healthy and gradually improving profitability (average NPM above 10%).

Table 1.1.2 Correlation between board size and net profit margin showing the dependent and independent variables (X, Y)

BOARD SIZE (X)	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
7	8.2	49	67.24	57.4
7	8.7	49	75.69	60.9
8	9	64	81	72
8	9.5	64	90.25	76
8	10.2	64	104.04	81.6
9	11	81	121	99
9	10.8	81	116.64	97.2
9	10.8	81	116.64	97.2
10	12.5	100	156.25	125
10	13.4	100	179.56	134
$\Sigma = 85$	$\Sigma = 104.1$	$\Sigma = 733$	$\Sigma = 1108.31$	$\Sigma = 900.3$

H₀: There is no significant relationship between Yale Foods PLC corporate governance practices and profitability.

TEST STATISTIC

$$r = \frac{n (\sum XY) - (\sum X) (\sum Y)}{\sqrt{[n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2] [n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

SIGNIFICANCE LEVEL

$\alpha = 0.05$ confidence

DECISION RULE

The null hypothesis is rejected if the r-cal > α -value at 0.05 otherwise, it is not rejected.

Manual calculations using the correlation formula

$$r = \frac{10(900.3) - (85)(104.1)}{\sqrt{[10(733 - 7225)] [10(1108.31 - 10836.81)]}}$$

$$r = \frac{9003 - 8848.5}{\sqrt{[7330 - 7225] [11083.1 - 10836.81]}}$$

$$r = \frac{154.5}{\sqrt{[108] [246.29]}}$$

$$r = \frac{154.5}{163.09}$$

$$r = 0.947$$

CONCLUSION

- Since $r = 0.947$, the correlation is **very strong, positive, and significant**.
- At $\alpha = 0.05$, the critical t-value for $n = 10$ ($df = 8$) was determined. Then t-tab is about **0.632**. (from the statistical table)
- Because $0.947 > 0.632$, we **reject the null hypothesis (H_0)**.

A strong and statistically significant positive relationship exists between board size and net profit margin of Yale Foods PLC. This means that as board size increases, the firm’s profitability (NPM) also improves.

Table 1.1.2 Correlation working table on institutional ownership and net profit margin showing the dependent and independent variables (X, Y)

Ownership Institutional (X)	Y	X^2	Y^2	XY
40	8.2	1600	67.24	328
41	8.7	1681	75.69	356.7
43	9	1849	81	387
45	9.5	2025	90.25	427.5
46	10.2	2116	104.04	469.2
48	11	2304	121	528
50	10.8	2500	116.64	540
52	10.8	2704	116.64	561.6
54	12.5	2916	156.25	675
56	13.4	3136	179.56	750.4
$\Sigma = 475$	$\Sigma = 104.1$	$\Sigma = 22831$	$\Sigma = 1108.31$	$\Sigma = 5023.4$

H_{02} : Ownership structure has no significant effect on Yale Foods PLC’s financial performance

TEST STATISTIC

$$r = \frac{n(\Sigma XY) - (\Sigma X)(\Sigma Y)}{\sqrt{[n \Sigma X^2 - (\Sigma X)^2] [n \Sigma Y^2 - (\Sigma Y)^2]}}$$

LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE

$\alpha = 0.05$ confidence

DECISION RULE

The null hypothesis is rejected if the p-tab $>$ α -value at 0.05 otherwise, it is not rejected.

Manual calculations using the correlation formula

$$r = \frac{10 (5023.4) - (475) (104.1)}{\sqrt{[10 (22831 - 225625) [10(1108.31 - 10836.81)]}}$$

$$r = \frac{50234 - 49447.5}{\sqrt{[228310 - 225625] [11083.1 - 10836.81]}}$$

$$r = \frac{786.5}{\sqrt{[2685] [246.29]}}$$

$$r = \frac{786.5}{813.197}$$

$$r = 0.967$$

CONCLUSION

Because **0.967 > 0.632**, we **reject the null hypothesis (H₀₂)**. A strong and statistically significant positive relationship exists between institutional ownership and profitability (NPM) of Yale Foods PLC. This implies that as institutional investors hold more shares in the company, the profitability tends to improve significantly consistent with the corporate governance literature that links institutional ownership with stronger monitoring and better performance.

The findings of this study show that corporate governance plays a critical role in shaping manufacturing firms' profitability and overall performance. Yale Foods PLC demonstrated that firms with stronger governance structures consistently record higher net profit margins and greater financial stability. The analysis confirmed that when well-structured, board size contributes positively to profitability by ensuring diversity of expertise and balanced decision-making. Furthermore, the study established that institutional ownership significantly improves firm performance, as large investors demand accountability and discourage mismanagement.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are recommended. First, manufacturing firms in Nigeria should strengthen their board structures by ensuring an optimal mix of executive and non-executive directors and, promoting gender and professional diversity for effective decision-making. Second, companies should encourage greater institutional ownership because institutional investors enhance monitoring and reduce the risk of managerial opportunism. Third, strict adherence to the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance should be enforced to promote accountability, transparency, and investor confidence.

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